

Driving the design of a telescope for Advanced Virgo+ with back-scattered light characterization

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Abstract

In the context of the installation of new stable recycling cavities foreseen for the next Advanced Virgo+ phase 2 upgrade scheduled in 2025–2027, a new telescope will be developed and installed on the optical bench used to detect the interferometer output beam. In order to help identifying the best design for this telescope, a test campaign is being carried out on the scatter meter at LAPP to test refractive and reflective optics and quantify the contribution to back-scattered light of each type of considered telescope configurations – those with low-incidence curved mirrors or a simple telescope with lenses. This article will introduce this backscatter meter, show preliminary results obtained with this experiment and give some perspectives for the backscatter meter experiment.

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Introduction

The sensitivity of gravitational wave detection interferometers is impacted by backscattered light, which can recombine and interferes with the main beam creating unwanted background noise [1]. This risk of interference is particularly acute when the light is back-scattered along the direction of propagation of the incident beam [2]. Backscattered light can originate from defects on optical components such as surface imperfections, optical coatings or interference with other optical components [3].

In the context of the Advanced Virgo+ phase 2, we are currently evaluating two distinct telescope configurations intended for the new stable recycling cavity detection bench: one featuring curved mirrors at low angles of incidence, and another using a simpler lens-based system. The principal goal of this study is to assess the performance of these two optical designs (reflective and refractive) specifically in relation to their impact on backscattered light. An experiment called the backscatter meter [4] has been set up to measure backscattered light from optics intended to be deployed on the optical benches used to extract the Virgo interferometer beams.

1 Evaluation of Telescope Configurations for Backscattered Light

A comprehensive campaign to measure backscattered light has been carried out using different window types, including those with HR and AR coatings. To perform this evaluation, we have characterized various optical components, including flat mirrors and windows, the window will serve as surrogate lens with same polishing quality as mirrors. The components under consideration include high reflectivity (HR) mirror optics, which function as harmonic splitters reflecting at 1064 nm while remaining transparent at 532 nm; uncoated windows; and AR windows with two differing coating types—one designed for standard anti-reflection and the other functioning as harmonic splitters that reflect at

532 nm and transmit at 1064 nm. Additionally, we have utilized recent measurements conducted on Faraday isolators from EGO, which have provided valuable data for our assessment of expected backscattered light from other components located on Virgo optical benches. A significant challenge in this evaluation is ensuring that the optical quality and polishing standards are comparable between the substrates with AR and HR coatings. This is crucial to accurately measure the performance differences between the two designs, rather than simply reflecting variations in mirror quality. To address this concern, we selected optics from Edmund Optics, as they have assured us the level of polishing quality consistent between the different types of optics. Our ongoing research aims to provide insights into the optimal design choices for minimizing backscattered light, thereby enhancing the sensitivity and performance of the Virgo detection system in its advanced phase.

2 Back-scatter meter SETUP

The back-scattered meter system uses the principle of homodyne detection by measuring the difference in power received by two photodiodes (see Figure 1). This difference in power between the two photodiodes comes from the light backscattered by the scattering sample moving on a suspended bench. The back-scattered light then returns to the beam splitter, some of it being reflected back to the laser and therefore lost, while the rest is reflected back to a second beam splitter used to transmit it to the two photodiodes by combining with the local oscillator beam. The laser power at the setup input is 14.2 mW, on the suspended bench 6.35 mW and on the two photodiodes 3.72 mW and 3.78 mW respectively.

Figure 1: Back-scatter meter experiment optical layout. The grey rectangle corresponds to the suspended bench (65 cm x 17 cm) on which two optics are fixed.

Initially, scattering sample were placed in the middle of the suspended bench to be measured because the waist of the beam was in the middle of the bench (275 mm from the bench edge). The telescope allowed the beam size to be adjusted to give a waist of the order of $280 \mu\text{m}$ in the middle of the suspended bench.

The configuration of this instrument has recently been changed to improve its sensitivity: the sample optic under study has been displaced at the end of the bench (650 mm from the bench input edge), and a reflecting mirror has been added at the other end of the bench in order to send the beam reflected by the sample onto a ground fixed beam dump. This ensures that the beam path length to the beam dump is fixed, and that the back-scatter from the beam dump is excluded from

the measurement. In the new configuration, the size of the beam is larger and now about 415 μm . However, the backscatter from the second reflecting mirror must be taken into account, and can be characterized in the same way.

3 Results

All measurements were conducted with an incidence angle of 7° . Figure 2 presents the bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) levels for mirrors and anti-reflective windows, all measured at the same incident angle. The teflon target acts as a verification of the correct calibration of the measurement with a measured BRDF of $\frac{1}{2\pi}$. The results show that the performance of uncoated windows was found to surpass that of high-reflectivity (HR) coatings, with the latter exhibiting higher levels of scatter. The BRDF of HR mirrors was significantly higher than that of anti-reflective coated windows, indicating that the backscatter factor of telescopes constructed with mirrors is greater than that of those utilizing lenses with anti-reflective coatings. Therefore telescopes employing lenses demonstrated a scattering rate at least ten times lower than those utilizing mirrors, despite incurring losses of 6000 ppm (see Table 1).

Figure 2: Measured BRDF for different optics characterized at $\theta = 7^\circ$. The dotted red line corresponds to the noise level of the instrument (without optics).

Table 1: **Reflectivity values for different optics taking into account the 2 faces.**

Optics	Reflectivity
HR mirror	> 99 %
AR window	0,16 %
Harmonic splitters	0,31 %
Uncoated window	8 %

For the Virgo project, we are aiming to achieve better coatings, targeting reflection losses on the order of 100 ppm per surface. If we consider the LMA coatings, we could potentially achieve around 100 ppm of anti-reflection per side, resulting in total losses of approximately 400 ppm for two lenses. In contrast, when evaluating coatings from Edmunds Optics, which exhibit a reflectivity of 0.16% per side, the total losses for two lenses would escalate to approximately 6000 ppm.

The Figure 3, extracted from [4], shows the level of BRDF as a function of the incidence angle obtained by measuring an AR window with the old configuration set up. If we compare the point

with an old measurement made on the scatterometer in the old configuration, it corresponds to an anti-reflective surface that was measured at 7° and has a BRDF of 7×10^{-6} . This is consistent with our measurements.

Figure 3: Figure extracted from [4]. Measured BRDF using a 2.1 mm radius beam (blue points) and 450 um radius beam (red points) as a function of incidence angle θ . The horizontal blue and red solid lines represents the corresponding measurement noise floor observed without a sample. The black solid line show the expected interference from the window 700 ppm specular reflection.

This Figure 4 illustrates the Bi-Directional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) as a function of reflectivity. When comparing the current data point in terms of reflectivity with the most recent measurements, we observe a notable proximity between the two points. This congruence suggests a consistent behavior in the reflectance characteristics, highlighting the reliability of our analysis.

Figure 4: Measured BRDF of different optics characterized as a function of the reflectivity.

4 Characterization of Virgo Output Faraday crystal backscattered light

In our investigation of the scattered light sources in SDB1 detection bench (see Figure 5), we focus on Faraday crystals which are used to attenuate the backscattered light of elements placed downstream of the Faraday. As they are one of the elements in the chain of the optical bench we characterized two Faraday isolators sourced from EGO : one that is 10 years old (named Faraday 12) and another that is 5 years old (named Faraday 13). Crystals were measured at various angles, starting around 20 mrad, corresponding to the angle of the TGG crystal used in the Virgo detection bench, and increasing it up to 220 mrad.

Figure 5: Detection bench SDB1 of Virgo.

The Figure 6 shows that at small incident angles, both Faraday isolators displayed similar levels of backscattered light. However, as the angle increased to 40 mrad, the performance of the Faraday 13 isolator improved significantly, demonstrating a backscatter reduction factor of 2.5 compared to the Faraday 12 isolator. This discrepancy is attributed to the better coating and more recent fabrication of the Faraday 13 isolator. To address the thicker crystals and potential Rayleigh scattering effects, we measured the impact of tilting the isolators at 220 mrad. Contrary to our expectations, tilting the isolators did not yield significant changes in scattering levels primarily due to two contributions to surface scattering : point defects and polishing quality of the surface. Indeed, the first surface point defects creates a constant Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) across angles, resulting in a flat curve in the scattering (see the red dots in the Figure 3). The second contribution, linked to polishing, causes scattering to increase significantly at very small angles due to surface irregularities (see the blue dots in the Figure 3). In our scenario, we systematically operated in a high-angle regime where scattering is mainly influenced by point defects and dust particles.

Figure 6: BRDF of TGG Faraday crystals 12 and 13 as a function of incidence angle θ .

In Figure 7, when comparing the BRDF values of the Faraday crystals to other characterized optics, it should be noted that the measurements did not correspond to the same angle of incidence. We have chosen to show on the plot only the crystal measurements done around 40 mrad, corresponding to the best performances of the Faraday crystal in terms of scattered light. We observe that the TGG crystals exhibited higher scatter than windows but lower than high-reflectivity (HR) mirrors. Importantly, strategic placement of optical elements becomes crucial: while telescopes utilizing HR coatings scatter more than TGG crystals and must be positioned post-Faraday isolator due to their increased backscatter, telescopes with lenses show significantly lower scattering—up to 100 times less than HR optics and approximately five times less than the Faraday isolator making the placement order less critical.

Moreover, the fraction of backscattered light (f_{sc}) from the entirety of the SDB1 bench was measured using the Virgo interferometer. The f_{sc} was found to be on the order of 3×10^{-10} for a beam radius of 1.3 mm [5]. The f_{sc} of the Faraday isolator was found to be approximately five times lower than that of the total back-scattered light of the entire SDB1 bench, indicating that the Faraday isolator is a significant contributor to backscattered light noise although not the only one (Table 2).

Table 2: The f_{sc} of the Faraday crystals are estimated for a beam size of 1.3 mm and an angle of incidence of 1.1 deg, so that they can be compared with the f_{sc} of the SDB1 bench.

Optics	f_{sc}	Reflectivity
TGG faraday 12	$6,6 \times 10^{-11}$	1,89 %
TGG faraday 13	$5,4 \times 10^{-11}$	0,31 %
All SDB1 $r= 1,3$ mm	3×10^{-10}	x

Figure 7: Measured BRDF for different optics characterized. The dotted red line corresponds to the noise level of the instrument (without optics).

Critically, our results suggest that positioning the Faraday isolator before the telescope reduces backscatter significantly. Given that the Faraday isolator effectively attenuates the backscattered light from subsequent optical elements by a factor greater than 1000, it stands as one of the principal contributors to backscattered light noise in the SDB1 configuration. However, the current design of the telescope on the SDB1 bench, which includes two parabolic mirrors and one meniscus lens positioned upstream of the Faraday isolator, suggests that additional scattering may arise from the second parabolic mirror, responsible for a substantial portion of scattered light. The beam is smaller on the second parabolic mirror (beam radius $w=1.3$ mm) than on the first parabolic mirror and the meniscus lens (beam radius $w=22$ mm), which is why the contribution of the M2 parabolic mirror is expected to dominate.

5 Calculation of expected scattered light on the detection bench SDB1

To assess the contributions of different optical components to backscattered light on the detection bench SDB1, we calculated the expected fraction of backscattered light from the high-reflectivity (HR) mirror positioned at an angle of 7° . Our calculations yielded a scattering factor f_{sc} of 5.36×10^{-11} . Similarly, for the TGG crystal situated at an angle of 1° , we obtained a scattering factor of $f_{sc} = 5.4 \times 10^{-11}$ (Table 3). Given that the beam radius is 1.3 mm, these results indicate that the contribution of the HR mirror to backscattered light is comparable to that of the TGG crystal in the current configuration of the bench. This finding highlights the importance of both components in the overall scattered light budget.

Table 3: The calculated f_{sc} of the Faraday crystal and the HR mirror placed on SDB1 bench done for a beam size of 1.3 mm.

Optics	Angles on SDB1 bench	f_{sc}
TGG cristal on SDB1	1°	$5,4 \times 10^{-11}$
HR mirror	7°	$5,36 \times 10^{-11}$

6 Characterization of HR mirror with a 45 deg incidence angle on SRB bench

Then we investigate the anticipated scattered light contributions from the folding mirror positioned before the Faraday isolator (FI) on the future detection bench, designated as SRB. As illustrated in Figure 8, the SRB design incorporates a high-reflectivity (HR) mirror fixed at an angle close to 45 degrees, preceding the Faraday isolator and the telescope is placed in a second bench after the Faraday isolator.

Figure 8: Future detection benches [6].

The measurements on an HR mirror at a 45-degree incidence reveal a backscattered light fraction of approximately 1.4×10^{-10} with a beam radius of 0.4 mm. For the future bench configuration, with an increased beam radius of 2 mm, we observe a significantly reduced backscattered light fraction of around 6.2×10^{-12} . Moreover, when considering the Faraday isolator set at a 1 degree angle, the backscattered fraction is found to be approximately 2.7×10^{-11} (Table 4).

Table 4: **The estimated f_{sc} of the Faraday crystal and the HR mirror placed on the future detection bench done for a beam size of 2 mm.**

Optics	Beam size [mm]	Angle	f_{sc}
HR	2	45°	$6,20 \times 10^{-12}$
TGG	2	1°	$2,71 \times 10^{-11}$

Our measurements with the HR mirror at various angles (7°, 20° and 45°) performed at LAPP (see Figure 9) indicate that the Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) decreases with increasing angle of incidence.

The contribution of the TGG is estimated to be four times greater than that of the HR mirror, indicating that the TGG remains the dominant source of scattered light. Furthermore, positioning the telescope after the TGG can reduce the amount of back-scattered light.

Figure 9: These are measurements of standard quality HR mirrors. On SDB1 we measure higher quality polished mirrors (around 0.3 nm RMS), so the scatter from the mirrors present on SDB1, and the ones which will be installed on SRB should be smaller.

Overall, the design of the future detection bench demonstrates a promising configuration for minimizing scattered light noise, contributing to enhanced performance in future experiments.

Conclusions

In evaluating the optical configuration for the SDB1 bench setup, the advantages and disadvantages of using lenses versus mirrors have significant implications for scattered light management. Lenses, particularly those with anti-reflective (AR) coatings, demonstrate a marked reduction in backscatter at least ten times less power than mirror systems and a factor up to 100 of reduction in small-angle backscatter. However, this benefit comes with increased optical losses and potential ghost reflections.

The choice between these configurations should consider several factors, including overall losses, scattered light, and tunability. Our analysis suggests that the configuration's impact on backscatter must be central to the decision-making process, particularly regarding the placement of the Faraday isolator.

Notably, positioning the Faraday isolator before the telescope minimizes backscattered light noise. Therefore, configuring all telescope components downstream of the Faraday isolator may provide an effective strategy for mitigating scattered light noise in the SDB1 setup.

The study does not give us the decision that the Virgo collaboration should make, but at least it tells us what impact scattering has on the different choices between using mirrors, lenses, placed before or after the Faraday isolator.

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